

Opinion | Architecture and Pandemics; How architecture can be the cure

Where Modernism and its subsequent influences could have strived

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Aalto's Paimio Sanatorium, Finland, 1929-1933

Although historians usually cite lack of functionality and rebellion against hierarchical architecture as the reasons for the less than a generation shift in architectural style, an often-forgotten reason that arguably and primarily aided the wide and rapid acceptance of a radical change in design style is **safety** or at least the perception and feel of it. Much of modernist architecture can be understood because of the fear of disease, a (subconscious) desire to eradicate dark rooms and dusty corners where bacteria lurk. Fixtures and surfaces that demonstrate cleanliness were emphasize, such as; plain white walls as opposed to ornamental walls, use of cement as opposed to the use of earth materials, bare floors and

clean metal fixtures as opposed to dusty wooden floors and bulky columns, larger windows to emphasize the need for light as opposed to limited window size hindered by design.

I believe that the best way to determine a possible solution is to study the approach employed in solving pandemics in history, of which there are many lessons we can draw from to address pandemics in the world today. There is a rich history of architectural solutions that have been employed to promote public health and hygiene, which can serve as a guide for contemporary architects. *Le Corbusier* lifted his houses off the humid ground to avoid contamination. *Adolf Loos's* ultra-boxy Villa Müller in Prague, from 1930, included a separate space in which to quarantine sick children. The Finnish architect and designer *Hugo Alvar Henrik Aalto*, along with his first wife, *Aino*, exemplified this trend even further in 1933 in the now-famous tuberculosis treatment facility, the *Paimio Sanatorium*, in southwest Finland. Finland had suffered the greatest loss of life to tuberculosis across the European countries and the design by *Alvar and Aino Aalto* is widely regarded as the first example of modern architecture applied to healthcare. Hygiene was the main principle that ran through the entire design process, with no pharmacological treatment for tuberculosis, *the Aaltos* turned to the curative effects of access to light, air, and sunlight from the windows to shape their architectural response. The building is rigidly geometric, with long walls of expansive windows wrapping its façade, light-coloured rooms, and a wide roof terrace with railings where patients could sleep, was part of the treatment, as sun proved effective at killing tuberculosis bacteria. Along with the building, *the Aaltos* also designed the sanatorium's furniture and tableware, conceiving a sort of total artwork aimed at improving people's health and well-being in a peaceful environment. At the *Paimio Sanatorium*, the architecture itself was part of the cure.

Architecture and Epidemics; on pre-modernism “solutions”

Pesthuis in Leiden, Netherland

After a spread of unknown infection, one of the first things pre-modernists did when an eventual epidemic was approaching was to start building plague houses, or “*pesthuis*”, buildings where the sick or those suspected to be infected could be treated with public funding. Sometimes they were large, planned, brick or stone structures, like the *pesthuis* in Leiden, Netherlands, complete with a moat, and gardens. These projects provided jobs when most needed and could employ “peasants” that would otherwise risk spreading the epidemics to other towns. Since every city, town, village, or even farm, had to provide for their own sick, some plague houses were built to house at most one individual or a household, should they need to be quarantined. In absolute emergencies, many towns up to the early 20th century had stocks of tents, and before that, disposable straw huts which could be set up easily, cheaply, and quickly (also widely used during World War I & II to treat injured soldiers), sunlight and fresh air was an added bonus.

Religion (particularly the Catholic Church) playing a vastly important role in many of history's successful epidemic solutions, primarily because of the church willingness to treat any and all infected person regardless of societal status. One of such successful epidemic solution was the wiping out a particularly bad plague (after the infection rate spread among both the rich and poor) in Rome in 1656 by Cardinal Girolamo Gastaldi (1615-1685) who was hired by the Pope as Commissary General of Health, giving him jurisdiction over the whole city. Plague houses were built as extensions to monasteries, the monks who had the know-how, the resources (medicine, food), the medical skills, and reliable, century-old, information networks, were well placed to supervise and direct epidemic control and treatment.

As opposed to the London elite treatment of the early 17th century plague. Covent Garden, the first planned (though unfinished) suburb, was conceived by the fourth Earl of Bedford as housing for an elite population away from the crowded streets of the city and the diseases that abounded there. Epidemics are even arguably responsible for touring repertoires; it was common in Tudor times for the royal court to leave London in the summer to avoid the outbreaks of contagion and sickness brought about by the hot weather. This rural retreat ran the risk of contagion following it, but it also brought culture and entertainment to the rest of the country with musicians and actors following the royal progress.

Perhaps, the rise of modernism in the health sector, its fast incorporation among the ethos of the common man, and it perceived synonym with cleanliness and safety, is an act of protest of our collective consciousness seizing our individualism from the status quo of the European elite and the charity and dependence of the catholic church.

Lessons From History

One of the most important lessons we can learn from history is the importance of flexible design. Traditional architecture often prioritized flexibility, designing spaces that could be easily adapted to meet changing needs. This flexibility allowed for quick responses during times of crisis, such as the adaptation of buildings into makeshift hospitals during pandemics. As an architect, we can create buildings that can be easily transformed to meet evolving needs.

Another important solution to pandemics is the integration of natural ventilation and airflow systems. Designing a building to promote natural ventilation, with open windows and airflow systems that allow for the expulsion of contaminated air helps to curtail the transmission of airborne pathogens.

Hygiene is another crucial consideration. Historical design solutions often emphasized the importance of clean surfaces, with buildings designed to minimize the accumulation of dust and bacteria. Features such as smooth, easy-to-clean surfaces, and materials like plaster, limestone, and other non-porous materials were often prioritized. We can employ these same materials and design features in our contemporary designs to promote hygiene and cleanliness.

Spatial planning is another area in which architects can draw inspiration from history in addressing pandemics. Incorporated open courtyards, wider corridors and other outdoor spaces to promote the circulation of fresh air and reduce the risk of transmission. Designs that facilitate and allow for physical distancing, strategic seating arrangements, and adaptable gathering areas ensure that individuals can navigate public spaces safely. This approach seeks to integrate the indoor with the outdoors, promoting a harmonious coexistence with nature.

Finally, biophilic design elements can be another key solution, especially for quarantine building. Throughout history, architecture has often incorporated natural elements such as plants, water features, and natural light to promote well-being and healing. These biophilic design features have been shown to have a positive impact on mental health and can help reduce stress during a pandemic. Beautiful sceneries psychologically soothe.

Modernism and its subsequent influences in today's crisis

During the COVID-19 outbreak of 2020, we were asked to be in our home indefinitely while the enemy was made out to be the streets, public spaces, public transport, and even loved ones, more than the virus. It has been almost a year now and our houses are still presumably the safe space, the problem though is, the modernist aesthetic and minimalist lifestyle have become shorthand for good taste; our homes and offices are of a long, plain, rectilinear design with cold, blank austere simplicity. It is unimpressively banal and depressing. As suicide rates reportedly increased globally and, in some areas, even more than the rate due to the virus, it has become clear that the only reason we condone banality and even outright ugliness is that we as designers and users lack long-term introspection with what we design and use. The architect designs and builds models but never lives out the experience of the design, while the user spends chunks of the day moving from one space to another without fully experiencing said design. Just like in the past, tragic events propelled architect to push the boundaries in search of smarter solution such as how the Great Chicago Fire of 1871 pushed Chicago into the age of cement and steel evolution. There is no doubt that architect around the world have picked up on the cause of the problem and are working to change and bring about a new age of a collective architectural style, one that would turn our home not to a four walled prison but to a castle, one that demands beauty.

“Beauty will save the world” – Fyodor Dostoyevsky